
Visible Phenotypic Markers as Early Indicators of Hyperactivity and Inattention in Preschool-Aged Children

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Abstract

This observational study investigates associations between two visible phenotypic traits, hair colour and craniofacial sweating, and behavioural features among children aged 4–6 years in Central Kerala. Based on parental reports, we investigated whether brown-haired children and those with excessive craniofacial sweating show higher rates of hyperactivity and inattention compared to their black-haired peers. The findings reveal that brown hair colour and excessive craniofacial sweating were each linked to a higher likelihood of hyperactivity or inattention, and these traits tended to co-occur. These results suggest that simple, observable characteristics may offer preliminary clues to behavioural patterns that warrant further study.

Because structured assessments are often delayed until these symptoms are evident, identifying additional observable markers in younger children may provide valuable opportunities for earlier detection and intervention.

Emerging evidence suggests that phenotypic features may be associated with behavioural dysregulation [6-8]. Visible traits might be relatively easy to notice, particularly by parents or primary caregivers, who can provide valuable insights into early behavioural differences that are often difficult to capture through formal testing in young children. Exploring such phenotypic-behavioural correlations could therefore open new possibilities for early detection and preventive support in childhood behavioural disorders.

Introduction

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is one of the most common neurodevelopmental conditions in children, characterised by impairing levels of inattention, impulsivity, and hyperactivity [1,2]. It affects learning, social relationships, and emotional regulation, and often persists into adolescence and adulthood, influencing academic achievement and overall quality of life [1-3]. Formal ADHD diagnosis requires at least six symptoms of inattention or hyperactivity-impulsivity (for children up to age 16), and epidemiologic data indicate that this diagnosis typically occurs around age 6, with cases rarely identified before age 4 [4,5].

Hyperactivity and inattention are well-established behavioural associated with eventual ADHD diagnosis [1]. Over several decades of my paediatric clinical practice, I observed recurring patterns suggesting that children with brown hair and prominent craniofacial sweating often exhibited higher levels of hyperactivity and inattention compared to those with black hair. These observations point to potential developmental links between phenotypic traits and behavioural tendencies. Notably, unlike hyperactivity and inattention, these phenotypic traits are observable from infancy, potentially allowing earlier identification of children at risk.

Motivated by these observations, the present study was undertaken to systematically explore

the relationship between hair colour, sweating patterns and behavioural traits indicative of ADHD- specifically inattention and hyperactivity in a cohort of preschool children.

Methodology

Data for this observational study was obtained from records collected by the investigator during routine pre-learning check-up visits. The dataset included 186 children aged 4–6 years. No formal sample size calculation was performed, as the study was exploratory in nature and aimed to identify potential associations between visible phenotypic traits and behavioural characteristics.

Data were collected exclusively through parental reports using a yes/no questionnaire regarding hair colour, sweating tendency, and behavioural traits (hyperactivity and inattention). No formal psychometric or clinical testing was performed. A child was classified as positive for a trait if it was reported by the parent and these responses were used to categorise the phenotypic and behavioral variables described below.

- Phenotypic markers: Hair colour was classified as brown or black. Sweating was recorded as excessive sweating or normal.
- Behavioral symptoms: Hyperactivity (HA) and inattention (IA) were recorded as behavioural traits indicative of ADHD.

Associations between hair colour, sweating, and behavioural features were examined using Fisher’s exact tests. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant. Effect sizes were reported as odds ratios (OR) and relative risks (RR) with 95% confidence intervals. All analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.0 (San Diego, CA, USA).

Ethics statement: This study analyzed anonymized data collected by the investigator during routine pre-learning check-up visits. Parents were verbally informed that the information will be used for research purposes, and only those who provided verbal assent were included. No personal identifiers were recorded or stored. Given that the study

involved minimal risk, used de-identified data, and was conducted in a setting without an institutional ethics review board, formal ethics approval was not required.

Results

A total of 186 children aged 4–6 years were included in the analysis. The distribution of key demographic and phenotypic features, specifically, gender, hair colour, and craniofacial sweating status, is presented in Table 1. These

Variable	Category	n (%)
Gender	Male	110 (59)
	Female	76 (41)
Hair colour	Brown	47 (25.3)
	Black	139 (74.7)
Craniofacial sweating	Excessive	116 (62.4)
	Normal	70 (37.6)

Table 1. Distribution of demographic and phenotypic characteristics in the study cohort.

distributions provided the baseline characteristics for the cohort. Subsequent analyses focused on evaluating associations between the phenotypic traits and behavioural features.

We first examined whether hair colour was associated with hyperactivity or inattention. Among children with brown hair ($n = 47$), 40 (85.1%) exhibited HA or IA, while 7 (14.9%) did not. In contrast, among children with black hair ($n = 139$), 95 (68.3%) showed HA or IA, and 44 (31.7%) did not (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Children with brown hair were more likely to exhibit hyperactivity (HA) or inattention (IA) compared to children with black hair (Fisher’s exact test $p = 0.036$)

Fisher's exact test revealed a significant association between hair colour and HA/IA status ($p = 0.036$), with children with brown hair having higher odds of exhibiting HA or IA (OR = 2.65; RR = 1.25). These findings indicate that brown hair colour may be associated with a higher likelihood of exhibiting ADHD-related behavioural traits.

We then examined whether the second phenotypic trait, craniofacial sweating, was associated with behavioural features. Among children who exhibited excessive sweating ($n = 116$), 94 (81%) showed HA or IA, whereas 22 (18.9%) did not. In comparison, among children with normal sweating ($n = 70$), 41 (58.6%) exhibited HA or IA and 29 (41.4%) did not (Figure 2). Fisher's exact test revealed

Figure 2. Children with excessive sweating were more likely to exhibit hyperactivity (HA) or inattention (IA) compared to children with normal sweating (Fisher's exact test $p = 0.001$)

a significant association between sweating status and HA/IA ($p = 0.001$), indicating that children who exhibited excessive sweating were more likely to show ADHD-related behavioural features than those without sweating. The corresponding effect estimates (OR = 3.02; RR = 1.38) further support sweating as a meaningful phenotypic correlate of behavioural dysregulation.

Given that brown hair colour and excessive sweating individually showed associations with behavioural features, we then examined whether both these traits tended to co-occur. Among children with brown hair ($n = 47$), 78.7% (37/47) exhibited excessive sweating, whereas among children with black hair ($n = 139$), only 56.8% (79/139) showed excessive sweating (Figure 3). Fisher's exact test

indicated a significant association between hair

Figure 3. Children with brown hair showed a higher prevalence of excessive sweating than those with black hair (Fisher's exact test $p = 0.009$).

colour and sweating status ($p = 0.009$; OR = 2.81, RR = 1.39), suggesting that children with brown hair were more likely to display excessive craniofacial sweating than their black-haired peers.

Finally, to determine whether the combination of visible phenotypes had implications for more complex behavioural presentations, we evaluated whether the joint presence of brown hair colour and excessive sweating was associated with co-occurring hyperactivity and inattention symptoms (HA+IA). Among children who exhibited excessive sweating, HA+IA traits were more frequent in brown-haired children (21/37, 56.8%) than in black-haired children (30/79, 38.0%) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Brown-haired children with excessive sweating showed higher HA+IA prevalence (21/37, 56.8%) than black-haired children (30/79, 38.0%), though the difference was not statistically significant (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.072$; OR = 2.1; RR = 1.5).

Although this difference did not reach

statistical significance (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.072$), the odds of HA+IA positivity were approximately 2.1 times higher in the brown-haired sweating group, with a relative risk of 1.5. This trend suggests that with a larger sample size, the difference might become statistically significant.

Discussion

The findings of this study suggest that readily observable phenotypic traits such as hair colour and craniofacial sweating may have meaningful associations with behavioural tendencies in early childhood. Both brown hair colour and excessive sweating were linked to a greater likelihood of hyperactivity or inattention, indicating that these simple physical markers may reflect underlying biological or developmental factors linked to behavioural regulation. These findings suggest that visible phenotypic traits particularly hair pigmentation and sweating patterns may serve as early markers of underlying neurodevelopmental vulnerability. Furthermore, the tendency for these traits to co-occur suggests a possible shared developmental origin, linking peripheral phenotypic expression with central regulatory processes.

Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is increasingly recognized as a neurodevelopmental regulatory disorder involving impaired self-regulation of attention, motor control, emotion, and arousal [9]. These difficulties arise from developmental differences in fronto-striatal and fronto-limbic circuits, modulated by dopaminergic and noradrenergic signalling [10-12]. The behavioural features of overactivity, inattention, and poor arousal control represent outward expressions of these internal regulatory disturbances. Autonomic manifestations such as excessive craniofacial sweating may reflect the same regulatory imbalance at the physiological level. The sympathetic nervous system, which controls sweating, shares developmental and regulatory links with cortical-subcortical circuits implicated in attention and arousal regulation [11,12]. Thus, behavioural and autonomic

traits could co-occur as parallel expressions of a common neurodevelopmental dysregulation.

The neural crest hypothesis provides a plausible developmental explanation for the observed associations. Neural crest cells are a transient, multipotent cell population that emerges early in embryogenesis and migrates to diverse regions of the developing embryo [13]. Through a tightly regulated process of differentiation and migration, these cells give rise to a broad range of tissues, including melanocytes (responsible for hair and skin pigmentation), autonomic neurons (which regulate sweating and other involuntary processes), and peripheral sensory ganglia, including dorsal root ganglia, which relay sensory information to the central nervous system and integrate autonomic and behavioural regulation [13]. The involvement of dorsal root ganglia provides a direct link between peripheral sensory and autonomic pathways and central regulatory circuits, offering a mechanistic rationale for the co-occurrence of pigmentation, sweating, and early behavioural traits.

Genetic, epigenetic or environmental influences during neural crest differentiation can alter developmental trajectories [14-17]. Therefore, depending on the nature of these influences, the resulting outcomes can vary. In Kerala's warm and humid climate, excessive craniofacial sweating is a readily observable early marker in children exhibiting hyperactivity and attentional difficulties, providing a natural setting for this phenotypic exploration. In contrast, in cooler climates, dermatologic manifestations such as infantile eczema or xeroderma may represent analogous expressions of autonomic and sensory dysregulation.

Beyond elucidating potential developmental mechanisms, the current study also highlights the potential value of parental observations as early indicators of neurodevelopmental tendencies. While the current study does not formally validate the reliability of parent-reported traits, the associations observed between hair colour, sweating patterns, and behavioural features suggest that parents can serve as reliable first-level observers in early developmental surveillance. Indeed, previous research has demonstrated that parent-reported

traits and screening tools can provide meaningful early cues for identifying behavioural and neurodevelopmental risks in young children [18-20]. Raising awareness of readily observable markers such as brown hair, craniofacial sweating, and behavioural features can transform ordinary parental observation into an informal screening tool. For clinicians, these traits may offer an accessible early window to identify children who could benefit from closer developmental monitoring or early behavioural interventions.

While this study provides valuable insights into potential links between phenotypic traits and early behavioural dysregulation, several limitations should be acknowledged. The study included 186 preschool children from a specific geographic region, and no formal sample size calculation was performed. Expanding the sample to a larger population across diverse geographic locations would enhance generalizability. Additionally, the study cohort was aged 4–6 years, a period when hyperactivity and inattention are already more apparent; earlier assessment of these phenotypic traits in younger children and longitudinal follow-up to determine which children later develop ADHD would provide more definitive evidence of predictive validity. Given the exploratory design, only descriptive and basic inferential analyses were performed; larger studies using multivariate models are needed to confirm the independence of these associations. Furthermore, while parental observations provided useful initial insights, these reports are inherently subjective and were not independently validated in the current study, highlighting the need for corroboration with objective measures.

Future research could address these limitations in several ways. Larger, multicentric studies would help confirm and extend these findings. Incorporating objective physiological measures such as skin conductance, heart rate variability, and thermal imaging could clarify autonomic contributions to observed traits. Investigations into mid-gestational gene–environment interactions may elucidate causal mechanisms

linking neural crest–derived structures, pigmentation, and behavioural regulation. Finally, integrating these findings into public health initiatives by training parents and primary care providers to recognize early phenotypic–behavioural clusters could facilitate early identification and timely intervention in community settings.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a consistent association between hair colour, craniofacial sweating, and hyperactivity or inattention in preschool children, suggesting that visible phenotypic markers may serve as accessible early indicators of children at risk for ADHD and related neurodevelopmental regulatory disorders. These findings establish a framework for future research and potential early-intervention strategies in childhood behavioural disorders.

Acknowledgements

I acknowledge Lakshmi Hospital, Aluva for granting permission to use anonymised clinical data for this study.

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